

ARJMD

(Hard Copy)

E-ISSN : 2456-1045

- International Journal
- Most Cited Journal
- Peer Review Journal
- Indexed Journal
- Open Access Journal
- University Recognized Journal

RESEARCH JOURNAL

VOLUME - 49 | ISSUE - 1

ADVANCE RESEARCH
JOURNAL OF
MULTIDISCIPLINARY DISCOVERIES

MAY
2020

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOUNDATION

Specialized in academic publishings only

www.journalresearchijf.com

Analysis of factors affecting the performance of Toddler Posyandu in Tanah Bumbu Regency

ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE	NAME OF THE AUTHOR'S
<p>ISSN : 2456-1045 (Online) ICV Impact Value: 72.30 GIF- Impact Factor: 5.188 IPI Impact Factor: 3.54 Publishing Copyright @ International Journal Foundation Article Code: MDS-V49-I1-C2-MAY-2020 Category : MEDICAL SCIENCE Volume : 49.0 (MAY-2020 EDITION) Issue: 1(One) Chapter : 2 (Two) Page : 08-16 Journal URL: www.journalresearchijf.com Paper Received: 28.06.2020 Paper Accepted: 08.07.2020 Date of Publication: 31-07-2020 Doi No: 10.5281/zenodo.3969198</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">¹Siti Aisyah ²Syamsul Arifin ³Erida Widyamala ⁴Husaini ⁵Fauzie Rahman*</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>¹Master Student of Public Health Study Program, Faculty Of Medicine, Lambung Mangkurat University, Indonesia</i></p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>^{2,3}Medical Science Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Lambung Mangkurat University, Indonesia</i></p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>⁴Master of Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Lambung Mangkurat University, Indonesia</i></p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>⁵Departement of Health Service Management, Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Lambung Mangkurat University, Indonesia</i></p>

ABSTRACT

Good implementation of posyandu will have an impact on meeting the basic needs of the use of posyandu for child development. Good performance for posyandu shows better service to the community. Based on data, posyandu strata in Tanah Bumbu Regency consist of Primary strata 17.03%, Intermediate Strata 44%, Purnama Strata 31.12%, and Mandiri Strata 7.85%. This study aims to analyze the factors that affect the performance of posyandu in Tanah Bumbu Regency. This study was an observational analytic study with a cross sectional study design. Sample of 65 cadre coordinators using *Stratified* Random Sampling. The research instrument used a questioner. Analysis of the data by descriptive and statistical are chi square and multiple regression logistic. The results showed that Posyandu whose members received training would perform well ($p = 0,000$). Posyandu whose members are getting rewards according to their performance standards will be compliant ($p = 0,023$). Posyandu which infrastructure is complete or supportive would perform well ($p = 0,000$). Posyandu which has a combination of financing sources will have good performance ($p = 0,013$). Analysis using regression logistic multiple shows variabel means of infrastructure ($p = 0,003$; Exp.B = 13.935), training ($p = 0,004$; Exp.B = 9,980), rewards ($p = 0,009$; Exp.B = 11.685) and sources of financing ($p = 0,028$; Exp.B = 7.168) with a confidence level of 95%. There are the affect of training, rewards, infrastructure and funding sources with Posyandu performance, with the most dominant variabel of infrastructure facilities among the four variabels.

KEYWORDS: training, rewards, facility infrastructure, sources of financing, performance integrated healthcare center.

CITATION OF THE ARTICLE

Aisyah S., Arifin S., Widyamala E., Husaini., Rahman F. (2020) Analysis of factors affecting the performance of Toddler Posyandu in Tanah Bumbu Regency; *Advance Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Discoveries*; 49(2) pp. 08-16

*Corresponding Author

I. INTRODUCTION

Integrated Service Post (Posyandu) is a form of Community-Based Health Efforts (UKBM) that is managed and organized from, by, for and with the community in order to empower the community and provide facilities to the public in obtaining basic health services, primarily to accelerate the reduction in maternal and infant mortality rates (Kemenkes RI, 2011). Posyandu is divided into 4 strata namely Primary Posyandu, Intermediate, Purnama, and Mandiri. Primary Posyandu is a posyandu that is not yet stable, monthly activities are not routine, the number of cadres is less than 5. Intermediate Posyandu is a posyandu that has been able to carry out opening hours more than 8 times per year, the average number of cadres is 5 or more, the scope of main activities is still less than 50%. Purnama Posyandu such as the Intermediate Posyandu, the difference is the scope of the main activities is more than 50%, able to carry out additional programs, there are already healthy fund activities but the participants are still less than 50% of the family head (KK). Mandiri Posyandu such as Purnama Posyandu, the difference is that the Mandiri Posyandu participant in healthy fund activities has reached more than 50% of families (Kemenkes RI, 2013).

Good implementation of posyandu will impact on meeting the basic needs of child development will be good too, such as the achievement of a high enough immunization coverage. In the years before the crisis and an increase in life expectancy, otherwise if the posyandu's performance is not good as in monitoring the growth of children, the development of children's nutritional status can be disrupted (Kemenkes RI, 2011).

Based on data from the Tanah Bumbu District Health Office in 2019, 20% of toddler were not monitored due to lack of posyandu activities that are routinely carried out every month. In addition, the lack of implementation of posyandu also has an impact on the incidence of malnutrition in infants, where in 2019 there were 6% of toddler suffering from malnutrition that occurred in posyandu that were less active in their activities or Primary Posyandu. The small number of Mandiri Posyandu at present shows that the Posyandu's performance is not yet optimal. This can be seen from the posyandu strata in Indonesia in 2017, namely 33.61% Primary Posyandu, 39.86% Intermediate Posyandu, 23.62% Purnama Posyandu, and Mandiri Posyandu (2.91%) (Kemenkes RI, 2018). Based on the data of Tanah Bumbu Regency in 2018 the number of posyandus were 205 posyandus spread across 14 Puskesmas, consisting of Primary Strata 17.03%, Intermediate Strata 44%, Purnama Strata 31.12%, Strata Mandiri 7.85% (Tanah Bumbu Health Office, 2019). The posyandu strata are an illustration of

the performance of a posyandu. Performance can be caused by several factors that affect including training, rewards, infrastructure, and sources of funding.

Posyandu training needs to be done so that the posyandu is functioning properly. Cadre training is an activity effort carried out to improve the ability, knowledge, technical skills and dedication of cadres in providing services at integrated posyandus by increasing the quality and quantity of services on the day of home visit opening (Purnomo, 2014). Research conducted by Purnomo (2014) shows the affect of posyandu cadre training with posyandu management capabilities so that it has an impact on posyandu performance. Data according to BPMPD, Health Office and PLKB there are cadres who have received training as many as 15.68% and 84.32% who have not received training from 205 posyandu and 1307 cadres in Tanah Bumbu (Tanah Bumbu Health Office, 2019).

Rewards for posyandu cadres are also important. Rewards given to posyandu cadres vary by region, ranging from Rp. 50,000 to Rp. 200,000 (Wisnuwardani, 2018). Tanah Bumbu Regency in 2016 set an incentive of Rp. 50,000 per month to Posyandu cadres. From the data available from the Tanah Bumbu District Health Office, 58% of cadres received below 50,000 monthly payments and 42% cadres received 50,000 monthly payments (Tanah Bumbu Health Office, 2019). The facilities and infrastructure in the posyandu are one of the factors that affect the performance of the posyandu, the unavailability of complete equipment, the lack of materials or medicines and the inadequate physical condition where posyandu activities lead to a decrease in posyandu performance (MOH RI, 2010).

Posyandu funding sources vary from government, non-government organizations and the private sector. Based on data from the Tanah Bumbu District Health Office, Posyandu funding sources are from the government, 35% of Posyandu funding sources are added from the non-governmental sector and only 10% Posyandu are sources of funding from the private sector. Limited budget or posyandu funds affect posyandu activities and have an impact on posyandu performance (Tanah Bumbu Health Office, 2019). Wisnuwardani's research (2012) found that the government has a very important role in financing posyandu including incentives for posyandu cadres.

II. METHOD

Retrieval of data by cross sectional approach is a study to study the dynamics of the correlation between risk factors and effects, by way of approach, observation or data collection at one time (point time approach) (Notoatmodjo, 2012). This research was conducted at a posyandu in the working area of

Tanah Bumbu Regency from February to March 2020. The population in this study were all coordinators of 205 posyandu spread across 14 puskesmas in Tanah Bumbu Regency. The criteria for sample inclusion in this study are as follows:

1. Posyandu which has a cadre coordinator
2. Respondents as coordinators for at least 1 year
3. Coordinator at Posyandu with a minimum operational period of 1 year

The sample exclusion criteria in this study are as follows:

1. Posyandu that is not active
2. Coordinator who was not in place at the time of the study

The number of samples in this study was calculated by utilizing the formula of hypothesis testing for population proportions of precision proportions according to Lameshow (Husaini et al, 2018). The number of research samples were 65 people. Sampling in this study was conducted by using stratified random sampling technique. The independent variables in this study were posyandu cadre training, posyandu cadre rewards, infrastructure facilities and sources of financing. Meanwhile, the dependent variable is the performance of toodler Posyandu.

The research instrument for performance measurement uses posyandu performance appraisal from the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. Univariate analysis was performed using the Chi Square test, while multivariate analysis was performed using multiple logistic regression analysis. This research had previously been through Ethical Clearance and was approved by the Health Research Ethics Commission of the Faculty of Medicine, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin-Indonesia with Number 049 / KEPK-FKUNLAM / EC / 2020 declared ethical.

III. RESULTS

A) Univariate Analysis

Table 1. Distribution and Frequency of Posyandu Performance, Cadre Training, Cadre Rewards, Posyandu Infrastructure Facilities, and Posyandu Financing Sources in Tanah Bumbu Regency in 2019

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Posyandu Performance		
Good (Purnama, Mandiri)	23	35,4
Bad (Intermediate, Primary)	42	64,6
Posyandu Cadre Training		
Yes	26	40,0
No	39	60,0
Posyandu Cadre Rewards		
According to the Standards	26	40,0
Not in Accordance with Standards	39	60,0
Posyandu Infrastructure Facilities		
Complete	24	36,9
Not Coomplete	41	63,1
Posyandu Financing Sources		
Combination	20	30,8
Government	45	69,2
Total	65	100,0

Based on the frequency distribution of posyandu performance, the majority of it showed poor posyandu performance. Posyandu performance that is not good is the performance of weighing activities less than or equal to 8 times a year, the number of cadres in Primary Posyandu <5 and Intermediate Posyandu ≥ 5 but other posyandu activities <50% namely Average D / S Coverage, MCH Cumulative Coverage, Coverage of MCH Cumulative Family Planning, Cumulative Coverage for Immunization, Additional Programs and Coverage of Health Funds. Whereas the Posyandu's good performance is the performance of weighing activities more than 8 times a year, the number of cadres in the Primary Posyandu > 5 and other posyandu activities > 50%, namely the D / S Coverage Rate, MCH Cumulative Coverage, KB Cumulative Coverage, Immunization Coverage, Program Additional and Healthy Fund Coverage for Mandiri Posyandu , healthy fund coverage ≥ 50%.

Most cadres (60%) have not yet attended training. Posyandu cadres who have participated in training are cadres who have participated in training conducted annually by the Tanah Bumbu Health Office. The training that followed was toddler training and stunting training. In addition, the majority of posyandu cadre rewards are still not up to standard (60%). The Tanah Bumbu District Health Office standard is Rp. 100,000 per month. Most posyandu infrastructure is incomplete according to posyandu standards. Posyandu whose infrastructure support is a Posyandu whose activities are supported by a complete infrastructure in accordance with Tanah Bumbu District Health Office standards.

Based on the frequency distribution of Posyandu financing sources, if the results of the research, most Posyandu financing sources are only from the government. Posyandu which sources of funding comes from the government shows that Posyandu activities are fully supported by

government funds, while Posyandu which has a combination of financing sources is Posyandu whose activities are supported by funds from the government and non-government organizations.

B) Bivariate Analysis

1. Effect of Posyandu Cadre Training on Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Table 2. Analysis of the Effects of Posyandu Cadre Training on Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu District

Posyandu Cadre Training	Posyandu Performance				Total	p-value	PR	95% (CI)
	Good		Bad					
	n	%	n	%				
Yes	17	65,4	9	34,6	26	0,000	4,250	1,934-9,340
No	6	15,4	33	84,6	40			
Total	23	35,4	42	64,6	65			

Based on the Chi Square test results with a 95% confidence level, it was found that the value of $p = 0,000$ then H_0 was rejected ($p < 0.05$) which means that the training had a significant effect on the performance of toodler. The result of PR is 4,250 (95% CI 1,934-9,340) which means that posyandu cadres who received training produced 4,250 times better performance compared to posyandu where cadres did not receive training. From the results of this statistical test which p value < 0.25 , this variable was included in the multivariate analysis.

2. Effect of Posyandu Cadre Rewards on Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Table 3. Analysis of the Effects of Posyandu Cadre Rewards on Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Posyandu Cadre Rewards	Posyandu Performance				Total	p-value	PR	95% (CI)
	Good		Bad					
	n	%	n	%				
According to the Standards	14	53,8	12	46,2	26	0,023	2,333	1,189-4,581
Not in Accordance with Standards	9	23,1	30	76,9	39			
Total	23	35,4	42	64,6	65			

Based on the Chi Square test results with a 95% confidence level, the value of $p = 0.013$ is obtained, then H_0 is rejected ($p < 0.05$), which means that the reward has a significant effect on the performance of toodler Posyandu. PR results of 2.489 (95% CI 1.272-4.873), which means that posyandu cadres who get rewards according to standards produce 9,375 times better performance compared to posyandu whose cadres do not get rewards according to standards.

From the results of this statistical test which p value < 0.25 , this variable was included in the multivariate analysis.

3. Effect of Posyandu Infrastructure Facilities and Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Table 4. Analysis of the Effects of Posyandu Infrastructure Facilities and Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Posyandu Infrastructure Facilities	Posyandu Performance				Total	p-value	PR	95% (CI)
	Good		Bad					
	n	%	n	%				
Complete	16	66,7	8	33,3	24	0,000	3,905	1,879-8,115
Not Coomplete	7	17,1	34	82,9	41			
Total	23	35,4	42	64,6	65			

Based on the Chi Square test results with a 95% confidence level, it was found that the value of $p = 0,000$ then H_0 was rejected ($p < 0.05$), which means that the infrastructure had a significant effect on the performance of the toodler Posyandu. The result of PR is 3,905 (95% CI 1,879-8,115), which means that posyandu which has infrastructure support results in 3.905 times better performance compared to posyandu which infrastructure has no support. From the results of this statistical test which p value < 0.25 , this variable was included in the multivariate analysis.

4. Effect of Posyandu Financing Sources on Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Table 5. Analysis of the Effects of Posyandu Financing Sources on Posyandu Toddler Performance in Tanah Bumbu District

Posyandu Financing Sources	Posyandu Performance				Total	p-value	PR	95% (CI)
	Good		Bad					
	n	%	n	%				
Combination	12	60,0	8	40,0	20	0,013	2,455	1,312-4,590
Government	11	24,4	34	75,6	45			
Total	23	35,4	42	64,6	65			

Based on the results of the Chi Sqaure test with a 95% confidence level, $p = 0.013$ is obtained, then H_0 is rejected ($p < 0.05$), which means that the source of funding has a significant effect on the performance of toodler. PR results of 2.455 (95% CI 1,312-4,590), which means posyandu which sources of funding come from the government and the private sector produces 2.455 times better performance than posyandu which sources of funding from the government alone. From the results of this statistical test which p value < 0.25 , this variable was included in the multivariate analysis.

ADVANCE RESEARCH JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY DISCOVERIES

C) Multivariate Analysis

Table 6. Multivariate Test Results

No	Variable	sig.	Exp (B)	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
1	Posyandu Cadre Training	0,004	9,980	2,074	48,031
2	Posyandu Cadre Rewards	0,009	11,685	1,861	73,364
3	Posyandu Infrastructure Facilities	0,003	13,935	2,438	79,611
4	Posyandu Financing Sources	0,028	7,168	1,237	41,538

The data shows that all independent variables entered at the same time show the parameter estimation if the independent variable p value of the Wald test (Sig) <0.05, meaning that the independent variable has a significant partial effect on the dependent variable in the model. Based on the analysis of Variables in the equation in the appendix, the posyandu cadre training variable has a significant value of 0.004 with a Wald value of 8.236 and a regression coefficient of 2.301. The significant value is <0.05 so that Ho is rejected or that means posyandu cadre training has a significant partial effect on the performance of toddlers posyandu. The posyandu cadre reward variable has a significant value of 0.009 with a Wald value of 6.878 and a regression coefficient of 2.458. The significant value is <0.05 so that Ho is rejected or that means the posyandu cadre rewards have a significant partial effect on the performance of toddlers posyandu. The infrastructure variable has a significant value of 0.003 with a Wald value of 8.774 and a regression coefficient of 2.634. The significant value is <0.05 so that Ho is rejected or that means the infrastructure has a significant partial effect on the performance of toddler Posyandu. The funding source variable has a significant value of 0.028 with a Wald value of 4.827 and a regression coefficient of 1.970. The significant value is <0.05 so that Ho is rejected or, which means the source of funding has a significant partial effect on the performance of the toddler Posyandu.

Wald value along with a positive regression coefficient on the training variable shows that the posyandu cadre training variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of toddlers posyandu. The more cadres that are given training, the better the performance of posyandu for toddlers, conversely the less cadres who receive training, the less good the performance of toddlers Posyandu. The magnitude of the effect is shown by the Exponent Beta (Exp B) value of the training variable of 9,980, posyandu whose cadres receive training will be 9,980 times performing well compared to posyandu whose cadres do not receive training.

The Wald value along with the positive positive regression coefficient on the Posyandu cadre reward variable shows that the Posyandu cadre reward

variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of toddlers' Posyandu. The more appropriate the posyandu cadre's rewards are given, the better the performance of posyandu toddlers, on the contrary the more inappropriate the rewards given to posyandu cadres, the less good the performance of posyandu toddlers. The magnitude of affect is shown by the Exponent Beta (Exp B) variable of posyandu cadre rewards of 11,685, posyandu whose cadres get rewards according to the standard will be 11,685 times their performance will be better compared to posyandu whose cadres do not get reward according to the standard.

Wald value along with a positive regression coefficient on the infrastructure variable shows that the posyandu infrastructure facilities variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of toddlers' posyandu. The better the posyandu infrastructure facilities, the better the performance of posyandu toddlers, on the contrary the less good the posyandu infrastructure facilities, the poorer the performance of posyandu toddlers. The magnitude of the effect is shown by the Exponent Beta (Exp B) value of the posyandu infrastructure facilities variable of 13,935, the posyandu whose infrastructure supports will be 13,935 times its performance will be better compared to posyandu whose infrastructure facilities do not support.

Wald value along with a positive regression coefficient on the variable sources of financing shows that the Posyandu financing source variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of toddlers' Posyandu. The more sources of posyandu financing, the better the performance of posyandu toddlers, on the contrary the fewer sources of posyandu financing, the less good the performance of posyandu toddlers. The magnitude of the effect is indicated by the value of Exponent Beta (Exp B) of posyandu financing sources variable of 7.168, posyandu for which combined financing sources will 7.168 times its performance will be better compared to posyandu whose only source of financing is the government.

So it can be concluded that from all the independent variables that most dominantly affect the performance of posyandu for toddlers is the posyandu infrastructure facilities variable (p value = 0,000) with exponent beta value (Exp B) of 13,935, meaning that posyandu for which the facilities support or fully support 13,935 times the performance the posyandu for toddler is good compared to posyandu for which infrastructure is not supportive or incomplete. The second variable is cadre reward (p value = 0.009) with exponent beta value (Exp B) equal to 11,685, which means posyandu that gives rewards according to the

standard will be 11,685 times the performance of posyandu for toddler is good compared to posyandu which gives rewards not according to the standard. The third variable is training ($p = 0.004$) with exponent beta (Exp B) of 9,980, which means that posyandu whose cadres receive training will be 9,980 times their posyandu performance will be better compared to posyandu whose cadres do not receive training. The fourth variable is the source of financing (p value = 0.028) with the exponent beta value (Exp B) of 7.168, which means that posyandu which has a combination of financing sources will 7.168 times the performance of the underwriting posyandu well compared to posyandu where the source of funding is only from the government.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Effects between Posyandu Cadre Training and Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Based on the results of statistical analysis using the Chi Square test showed a p -value of 0,000 ($p < 0.05$) means that H_0 was rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between posyandu cadre training and the performance of posyandu toddlers in Tanah Bumbu Regency. Ratio Prevalence Value of 4,250 (95% CI 1,934-9,340). This means that posyandu cadres who received training had a 4,250 times chance of toddler posyandu performance for toddlers compared to posyandu whose posyand cadres did not receive training. The results of this study explained that posyandu whose cadres received training had better performance compared to posyandu whose cadres did not receive training.

The role of cadres is very important, because cadres are responsible for implementing posyandu. If the cadres are not active, then the implementation of posyandu will also be not optimal. The role of cadres greatly affects the level of success of the posyandu program, especially in monitoring child development and maternal health. According to Martinah (2008) only 40% of cadres are active in posyandu activities in Indonesia. Therefore, steps need to be made in empowering cadres to be more professional in monitoring child development and maternal health, as well as building community partnerships to increase support and utilize posyandu optimally. So that the empowerment of cadres is very important to optimize the Posyandu Revitalization (Martinah in Ikeu, 2014).

The results of this study are consistent with the results of Simanjuntak (2012) research that the training of posyandu cadres has an affect in improving their performance. The training program aims to improve

and develop the skills, expertise, skills and abilities of an employee, so that the company has skilled, competent, high employee performance and great responsibility towards the company. Likewise, a study conducted by Andira (2012) that training has a significant effect on the performance of posyandu cadres and ultimately has an impact on posyandu performance.

2. Effects between Posyandu Cadre Rewards and Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Based on the results of statistical analysis using the Chi Square test showed a p value of 0.023 ($p < 0.05$) meaning that H_0 was rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant effect between posyandu cadre rewards and the performance of posyandu toddlers in Tanah Bumbu Regency. Prevalence ratio value is 2,333 (95% CI 1,189-4,581). This means that posyandu cadres who do not receive rewards for posyandu cadres according to the standard have a 2.333 times chance that the performance of posyandu for toddler is not good compared to posyandu where posyand cadres receive rewards according to the standard. The results of this study explain that posyandu that gives rewards according to the standard to its cadres will have better performance compared to posyandu who provide rewards that are not up to standard to their cadres. Sharma (2011) in Yanti (2016) explained that incentives are one of the motivational tools for the Wolker female community health.

According to Abdullah (2010) incentives are an attraction for people to come and live in an organization which means that the payroll and implementation system needs to be developed in such a way that the incentive system is more than just wages for the work done. This is like a study conducted by Yanti (2016) reward / incentive factor is one part of the good level of cadre performance in two regions where Darussalam with Blang Bintang median (75% versus 75%) with the provision of incentives in the form of awards and materials is one of the best can motivate cadres to carry out their duties.

Based on the results of a posyandu study whose performance is rewarded according to standards, the performance is good. Mutiara (2002) explains that the incentives given to cadres greatly motivate its activity. According to Aprillia (2009), the low number of incentives received by posyandu cadres caused the lack of motivation in cadre performance and active participation. Providing incentives is a basic payment to motivate employees to advance in work with greater skills and responsibilities. Incentives are one type of award associated with work performance.

3. Effects between Infrastructure Facilities and Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Based on the results of statistical analysis using the Chi Square test showed a p value of 0,000 ($p < 0.05$) meaning H_0 was rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant affect between posyandu infrastructure and the performance of toddler in the Tanah Bumbu Regency. Prevalence ratio value of 3,905 (95% CI 1,879-8,115) this means that posyandu infrastructure facilities that support have the opportunity to have 3,905 times the performance of their toddler posyandu well compared to posyandu whose posyandunya infrastructure does not support it. The results of this study indicate that the more complete the infrastructure, the better the posyandu's performance.

According to Siagian (1998), posyandu activities will not be able to run well if they are not supported by adequate facilities. Provision of work facilities is that the work facilities provided must be sufficient and in accordance with the duties and functions and must be implemented and available at the right time and place. The Indonesian Ministry of Health (2010) explained that the existing facilities and infrastructure in posyandu are one of the factors that affect the performance of posyandu, the unavailability of complete equipment, the lack of materials or medicines, and the physical condition where the posyandu activities are inadequate cause a decrease in posyandu performance. In addition, the low performance of posyandus is also caused by training where posyandu cadres do not receive training so that they lack competence in carrying out their duties.

The results support the research of Murniati (2007) proving that the availability of services has an affect on the utilization of health services. Likewise, Hasanah's research (2012) also showed that the complete posyandu facilities had an affect on the performance of posyand cadres. In other words, the availability of adequate facilities at posyandu will increase the interest of mothers to bring their children to the posyandu.

4. Effects between Financing Sources and Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

Based on the results of statistical analysis using the Chi Square test showed a p value of 0.013 ($p < 0.05$) meaning H_0 was rejected. It can be concluded that there is a significant affect between posyandu financing sources and the performance of toddlers posyandu in Tanah Bumbu Regency. Prevalence ratio value of 2.455 (95% CI 1,312-4,590) this means that posyandu financing sources from the government and private sector have an opportunity of 2.455 times the

performance of the underwriting posyandu well compared to posyandu where the posyandunya funding source comes from the government.

Based on the results of the study, posyandu which has a combination of posyandunya performance financing sources is also good. This is because the posyandu's activities are inseparable from funds originating from government and private or non-government funding sources. The Indonesian Ministry of Health (2006) explained that posyandu funding is an important part of the quality of posyandu implementation, because funds are the main supporting facility in the activities of an organization. The funds needed to finance posyandu activities are collected from the spirit of togetherness and are used in an integrated manner from the community, the district / city, provincial, central government and private donations and others.

The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Musfika Rahman Badawi (2014) where the results of the study showed that there was a relationship between funding sources and Posyandu performance in Community Nutrition Development in the Work Area of Kembangan District Health Center, West Jakarta District in 2014. But this study was not in accordance with the research conducted by Nova Sylviani (2011) where the results of the study showed that there was an affect of funding sources with the performance of the elderly posyandu in the Miroto Puskesmas Work Area Semarang.

5. Effects of Posyandu Cadre Training, Posyandu Cadre Rewards, Infrastructure Facilities and Financing Sources to Toddler Posyandu Performance in Tanah Bumbu Regency

The results of multivariate analysis of four independent variables namely training variables, rewards, infrastructure facilities and sources of financing show that overall the training variables, rewards, infrastructure facilities and sources of financing have an affect of 84.6% on the performance of posyandu toddlers. The training regression line of 2.301 on posyandu performance in the form of positive toddlers means that the better the training provided to posyandu cadres, the better the performance of posyandu toddlers, the reward variable has a positive regression line of 2.458 meaning the more appropriate the rewards given, the better the performance of toddlers' posyandu, infrastructure facilities also have a positive regression line of 2,634 which means that the more support the infrastructure owned by the posyandu, the better the performance of the posyandu for toddlers as well as funding sources have a positive regression line 1,970 which means the more sources of posyandu financing, the better the performance of the toddler posyandu. The constant value has a negative

value of -14,141 meaning that if there is no training, the rewards are not according to the standard, the infrastructure is not supportive and the sources of funding are lacking, then the performance will decrease because it has a negative value.

Based on the results of the study showed that the infrastructure variable had the most dominant affect on the performance of posyandu for toddlers with an exp value (B) of 13,935, which means that posyandu whose infrastructure support or complete would have 13,935 times the posyadunya performance would be better compared to posyandu where infrastructure was not supportive or incomplete. In this study, infrastructure is the most dominant factor compared to compensation, training and funding sources, this is because activities that are not supported by complete infrastructure will not run well. Some posyandus do have their own buildings but not many in number. Posyandu buildings in the village are usually located on village land or community land donated by some posyandu to borrow the houses of residents or posyandu cadres. The availability of Educational Game (APE) equipment for some posyandus is complete and the conditions are good but some posyandus do not have complete equipment, I-V desk activities are also not available and hamper posyandu activities. Therefore, complete infrastructure is very important for conducting posyandu activities.

If the infrastructure is complete, then the support of cadre performance is an important factor, and this can be obtained if the cadre gets rewarded according to standards such as Rp. 100,000 every month. The results showed the reward variable had an exp (B) value of 11,685, which means that posyandu whose cadres received rewards according to the standard would be 11,685 times better performance compared to posyandu whose cadres did not get rewards according to the standard. Rewards will increase posyandu cadres' work motivation because after all Posyandu cadres work to spend time and energy so there needs to be incentives so that posyandu cadres can work more enthusiastically, so completeness of infrastructure is supported by cadre work motivation because the rewards will improve posyandu performance.

After the availability of complete infrastructure is added to the work motivation of cadres due to the provision of compensation according to the standard, then the next is the training factor where the results of the study show an exp (B) value of 9,980 which means that posyandu whose cadres receive training will be 9,980 times good performance compared to Posyandu whose cadres did not receive training. Support from skilled cadres will support the performance of

posyandu toddlers, because if cadres are skilled but not supported by adequate infrastructure, posyandu activities will be hampered because posyandu cadre skills can be improved by learning and guidance from health workers at the puskesmas and experience during becoming a cadre, even though training is also needed by cadres to carry out their duties. This can be seen from the results of research in which posyandu which infrastructure is complete even though the cadres are not trained, posyandu toddlers' performance is good because posyandu cadres during their duties are always under the guidance of health workers from the Puskesmas.

The last factor that affects after infrastructure facilities, rewards and training is the source of funding, this is because it is related to the ability of the community in providing funds where in Tanah Bumbu Regency the economic capacity of the community is different so that for self-help communities are still lacking in some villages. So far, most Posyandu funding sources have come from the government, but even though funding sources are only from the government, if the infrastructure supports, then it is supported by trained cadres and cadres who work to get rewards so that the work motivation of cadres increases. Moreover, if the available funds are sufficient for posyandu activities, this will be better. And vice versa if the posyandu is not supported by complete infrastructure, then the cadres have never received training, there is no reward for the cadres but the funds are sufficient, this certainly will not have a major impact on the performance of the toddler posyandu. So it can be concluded that the completeness of infrastructure is the most important thing to support posyandu activities and is supported by the work motivation of cadres because there is a reward according to the standard and the support of trained cadres afterwards the source of funding.

This research is supported by the research of Musfika Rahman Badawi (2014). The results of research on the performance of posyandu for toddlers is low, community self-sufficiency is still lacking. But this study is not in accordance with the research of Nova Sylviani (2011) where the results of the study Most of the cadre's performance is good (61.2%), good funding sources (82.1%), socialization is not good (68.7%), good service (65.7%), good infrastructure (65.7%) and the performance of posyandu for toddlers is good (59.7%). The analysis found that the performance of the cadres affected posyandu performance (p value = 0.001) and service affected posyandu performance (p value = 0.001). Sources of funding, outreach, and infrastructure did not significantly affect posyandu performance.

V. CONCLUSION

Posyandu cadre training, cadre rewards, infrastructure facilities, and financing sources affect the performance of posyandu toddlers in Tanah Bumbu Regency in 2019. Posyandu infrastructure facilities are the most dominant factors influencing the performance of toddlers' posyandu, after that training factors, then the posyandu cadre reward factors and the last source of financing. The Tanah Bumbu District Health Office needs to complete the posyandu infrastructure facilities such as building a place for posyandu activities, completing health equipment, educational play equipment for toddlers and other equipment to support cadres carrying out their duties. In addition, the Health Office needs to include cadres who have never received training to be included in trainings to improve the cadre's skills in carrying out their duties, and needs to evaluate the rewards given in each posyandu according to existing regulatory standards, the Health Office needs to pay attention to the amount of the budget given to posyandu tailored to the needs and activities of the posyandu so that posyandu activities can be carried out in accordance with their functions. Posyandu should make gradual proposals to local governments to complete infrastructure by inventorying existing infrastructure to be submitted to the government, proposing cadres to take part in training and proposing changes in incentives according to local government standards to local governments through the health department. In addition Posyandu needs to increase activities that can generate income for Posyandu so that Posyandu can more independently finance its activities.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] **Badawi.** Kinerja posyandu dalam pelaksanaan pembinaan gizi masyarakat di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Kecamatan Kembang Jakarta Barat Tahun 2014. Skripsi. Jakarta: Program Studi Kesehatan Masyarakat. Universitas Islam Negeri Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta; 2014.
- [2] **Depkes RI.** Pedoman puskesmas santun lanjut usia bagi petugas kesehatan. Jakarta: Direktorat Bina Kesehatan Komunitas; 2010.
- [3] **Dinas Kesehatan Kabupaten Tanah Bumbu.** Data Posyandu. 2019.
- [4] **Dinas Kesehatan Kabupaten Tanah Bumbu.** Profil Kesehatan Tahun 2014. Online. Diakses dari <http://dinkes.tanahbumbu.kab.go.id> pada tanggal 11 Januari 2019.
- [5] **Hasanah.** Faktor-faktor yang berhubungan dengan kinerja kader posyandu di Kabupaten Bukit Kabupaten Bener Meriah Tahun 2012. Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat Stikes U'budiyah. Banda Aceh; 2012.
- [6] **Husaini.** Buku pedoman penulisan tesis. Unit Pengelola tesis S2 IKM Unlam Banjarbaru; 2018.
- [7] **Kemenkes RI.** Buku Panduan Kader Posyandu Menuju Keluarga Sadar Gizi. Jakarta. Kemenkes RI; 2011.
- [8] **Kemenkes RI.** Pedoman pelaksana posyandu. Sekjen Kementrian Kesehatan RI. Jakarta: Kementerian Kesehatan RI; 2011.
- [9] **Kemenkes RI.** Buku saku pelayanan kesehatan ibu di fasilitas kesehatan dasar dan rujukan. Edisi 1. Jakarta: Kementerian Kesehatan RI; 2013.
- [10] **Kemenkes RI.** Ditjen Bina Gizi dan KIA. Direktorat Bina Kesehatan Ibu Pedoman Pelayanan Antenatal Terpadu Edisi 2. Jakarta. Kementerian Kesehatan RI; 2013.
- [11] **Kemenkes RI.** Riset kesehatan dasar. Jakarta. Kemenkes RI; 2018.
- [12] **Murniati.** Faktor-faktor yang berhubungan dengan pemanfaatan pelayanan antenatal oleh ibu hamil di Kabupaten Aceh Tenggara. Tesis. Universitas Sumatera Utara; 2007.
- [13] **Notoatmodjo, S.** Metodologi penelitian kesehatan, Jakarta. PT. Rineka Cipta; 2012.
- [14] **Simanjuntak.** Karakteristik sosial demografi dan faktor pendukung kinerja kader posyandu. Jurnal Kesehatan. 2012; 4 (1).
- [15] **Sylviana, N.** Faktor-faktor yang berhubungan dengan kinerja posyandu lansia di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Miroto Semarang. Online. diakses pada: 12 September 2019 melalui <http://eprints.dinus.ac.id/id/eprint/17413>.
- [16] **Wisnuwardani, R.W.** Insentif uang tunai dan peningkatan kinerja kader posyandu. Artikel Penelitian. FKM Universitas Mulawarman; 2018.
